

TEXTBOOKS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *The article deals with the importance of motivational factors paid attention in the textbooks in our national context. Especially, as primary classes are dependent on motivation, their coursebook and activities were analyzed in the article.*

Key words: *motivation, integrative motivation, instrumental motivation, learning process, success, behavior, perspective.*

Motivation is one of the most essential factors which can give a chance for learners to learn autonomously in learning process. Without this factor in teaching it is impossible that learners especially, English learners can get succeeded.

There are some definitions for the term “Motivation” given by different scholars.

Motivation is the wrench of success in learning process. There are certain definitions of motivation from some experts according to Hayikaleng, Nair and Krishnasamy.

Motivation is regarded as an important component to make students success in their English learning. Motivation can also be defined as one's direction to behavior or what causes a person to want to repeat a behavior and vice versa [1]. Besides, Tambunan and Siregar also state that motivation and educational achievements as reflected in grade point average are positively correlated at all levels of schooling, elementary through college.

From a whole explanation above can be illustrated that motivation is the combination of attempt plus desire which gives the reasons for people's actions, desires, and needs to obtain the objective of learning towards an objective. According to Lai, motivation refers to reasons that underlie behaviour that is characterized by willingness and volition. Motivation involves a constellation of closely related beliefs, perceptions, values, interests, and actions

However, by getting motivation students will be spirited in learning, so they will be motivated to study English well. Teachers should be aware of significance of motivation in learners' language learning and through some changes they can help learners increase their motivation.

According to Rehman and Alizadeh, there are two types of motivations and they gave definitions below:

1. Integrative Motivation

Integrative motivated is the condition when the learners want to learn the target language so that they can better understand and get to know the people who speak the language and mix up in their culture [1].

2. Instrumental Motivation

Integrative motivation describes learners who want to integrate themselves into the culture of the second language group and become involved in social interchange in that group.

Motivation is a multifaceted concept that has been the subject of scholarly researches in different academic areas and no single available theory has yet captured its total complexity [2]. Gardner also confirmed that “motivation is a very complex phenomenon with many facets...thus it is not possible to give a simple definition.”[3:67]. This is because the expression of motivation has been investigated differently by different perspectives. On the behavioral perspective, motivation is “quite simply the anticipation of reward” [3]. Whereas the cognitive perspective views the term of motivation as being more related to the student's decisions, and the choices students make as to what experiences or goals they will approach or avoid, and the degree of effort they will exert in that respect. For the constructivists in their definition of motivation, they place further emphasis on the social context as well as the individual's decisions. Regardless of the differences in all the definitions of motivation given by the three different perspectives, the concept “needs” is emphasized, that is, “the fulfillment of needs is rewarding, requires choices, and in many cases must be interpreted in a social context” [3].

When we are thinking about integrative motivation in terms of Rehman and Alizadeh, it is important that extra materials are needed for teaching process especially, young learners. [5:18-19]

Now we are having a look at the instrumental motivation which is described in our local designed books. In 5th grade, every 6th lesson in the unit will be project work. In this way students can show their knowledge by doing portfolio and writing their over all reflection on the unit. In addition to that, a great number of pictures are provided as visual aids.

Conclusion, in our article we investigated the factors of motivation namely integrative and instrumental motivation in accordance with our local coursebook themes designed English learners in primary classes. Motivational points are paid attention vastly enough but only thing is that teacher would be able to use them in their lessons.

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